

AN EMC TEST PROCEDURE FOR AN ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPH (EEG)
USING HUMAN SUBJECTS AND SIMULATED ELECTRONIC PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

An electroencephalograph (EEG) is one of the most sensitive medical devices in use--it responds to microvolt levels of brain wave potentials. Can indicative EMC testing be conducted using the radiated field strength levels set forth in the EMC Standard for Medical Devices? Does the patient act as an effective antenna; or, could a substitute electronic patient be used? Is it possible to identify the susceptible EEG components? If so, can relatively cost effective shielding of these components be developed to improve the EEG's overall EMC to radiated fields? These and other aspects were considered and resolved over the frequency range from 50 kHz to 110 MHz.

INTRODUCTION

The Food and Drug Administration's Bureau of Radiological Health (BRH) has conducted laboratory tests on a current production model EEG to determine this device's susceptibility to radiated electromagnetic signals in the frequency range of 50 kHz to 110 MHz. This was done in cooperation with the FDA's Bureau of Medical Devices (BMD) in support of their development of a standard on electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) for medical devices.

The BRH received a request from the Veterans' Administration (VA) to evaluate EEG equipment for compliance with the proposed FDA EMC standard. The VA requested the testing to gain a quantitative insight as to the amount of external radiofrequency (rf) shielding that is necessary to obtain an interference-free EEG recording in a hospital environment (Ref. 1). The VA policy, at that time, was to install rf-shielded rooms in each area in which EEG would be used during the construction of a new hospital. If the rf interference characteristics for an EEG device, one of the more sensitive medical instru-

ments, were known, a better indication of the degree of shielding necessary could be determined. This could result in substantial cost reduction.

PROCEDURE

With the cooperation of a major EEG manufacturer, EMC tests were conducted on an eight channel EEG using passive loads, a BRH developed optically-driven electronic substitute patient, and three human volunteers. The passive loads tested were: 10 k and 24 k resistors; these resistors in parallel with 0.1 microfarad capacitors; and combinations of these resistors and capacitors with diodes. During preliminary testing, the 10 k resistors proved to be the best passive load; however, since no "brain wave" was being generated, one could not be sure if the EEG record was interference free or if it appeared so due to complete amplifier saturation. (In either case, a straight line "EEG record" would be observed.) This led to the development of an active electronic substitute patient which consisted of a light pulsed photodiode in parallel with a 10 k resistor (figs. 1 & 2). The gate indicator light of a frequency counter was found to be a suitable light source to pulse the photodiode. Its light pulses were optically coupled to the photodiode via a twenty foot (6.1 meters) light pipe; thereby, keeping the size of the electronic substitute patient, and its field perturbation potential, minimal. The electronic substitute patient's "brain wave" appeared as a continuous wave (CW) signal on the EEG record and was similar in both frequency and amplitude to the human alpha wave (i. e., 50 microvolts peak-peak at 8-13 Hz). A balanced parallel plate transmission line, driven with high power rf amplifiers, was selected for generation of the rf exposure fields.

The test spectrum was divided into nine swept frequency bands. This allowed the field leveling equipment (consisting of an E-field

sensor optically coupled to a leveling preamplifier) to be precisely operated so that the test subject would not be exposed to levels higher than intended. The optical-leveling cable was also the

mechanism by which the human volunteer, or the EEG technician, could at will immediately terminate the rf exposure field during the tests. (See figure 3 for a photograph of the exposure set-up.)

Figure 1: Component parts of the "Electronic Substitute Patient".

Figure 2: Assembled "Electronic Substitute Patient".

Figure 3: RF exposure set-up with parallel plate transmission line source, E-field leveling sensor, EEG, and chair for human volunteer.

For the human study portion, the exposure field was limited (at the volunteer's request) to a maximum of 1.5 Volts/meter (V/m). For the electronic substitute patient, and the passive loads, the exposure fields (30% AM sine wave modulated at 40 Hz) were as follows: 1.5 V/m and 2.0 V/m from 50 kHz to 550 kHz; 1.5 V/m and 2.0 V/m* from 550 kHz to 30 MHz; and, 1.5 V/m, 2.0 V/m and 4.5 V/m* from 30 MHz to 110 MHz.

RESULTS

This investigation indicated the following for the frequency range tested:

1. An electronic substitute patient, provided it is non-perturbing, can validly replace a human subject to test an EEG for radiated electromagnetic susceptibility. This was established for the BRH developed design by direct comparison with the human EEG records (see fig. 4).

*Field strength levels contained in the FDA EMC Standard for Medical Devices (see Ref. 2).

2. This EEG unit was susceptible to interference at certain frequencies in some of the test-frequency bands, while it functioned normally in others. (At these specific interference frequencies, the FDA EMC Standard (Ref. 2) could not be satisfied.) Based on these results, it appears that prior knowledge of the ambient electromagnetic environment (i. e. . field strength and frequency) at a proposed building site, for example, could modify the degree of shielding necessary for unaffected operation of the EEG.

3. Each of the eight channel's amplifiers "processed" the rf interfering signal differently at a given interference frequency. This can be seen in figure 4, at 22 MHz, for example. The amplifier for channel 7 (second trace from the bottom of the record) displays less interference than the amplifier for channel 3 (third trace from the top of the record). Physically interchanging the two amplifiers, (i. e. . placing amplifier 7 in channel 3's slot in the EEG console, and amplifier 3 in channel 7's slot), with nothing else changed, resulted in a reversed EEG record for these two channels. The minimum interference

Figure 4: RF interference from 18-26 MHz in B & C.

now appeared in the third trace from the top. The "processed interference signal" followed the amplifier; therefore, the amplifier's internal characteristics, rather than its location in the EEG console, determined the degree of interference displayed on the EEG record.

4. The primary receiver of rf energy, over the frequency range tested, was found to be the multi-conductor cable (see fig. 3) which connects the EEG console to the patient electrode board. Additional tests, using a transverse electromagnetic (TEM) transmission cell to expose only the multi-conductor cable, confirmed this by comparison with the EEG records obtained from the primary exposure set-up. The TEM cell also provided an additional set of data with which to compare the susceptibility of the original single-shielded multi-conductor cable with double-shielded multi-conductor cables, which were constructed by the EEG manufacturer, once it appeared that additional shielding would be beneficial for EMC.

5. Shielding the small electrode wires (see fig. 1), which connect the patient electrode board to the head of the volunteer, (or to the electronic substitute patient), resulted in little, if any, improvement in EMC.

6. In general, based on an overall frequency response, while using the primary test set-up, and the TEM cell, the following was observed: (a) For the 50 kHz to 10 MHz range, using the original single-shielded multi-conductor cable, an interference-free recording was obtained when the exposure field was reduced to 40 mV/m (fig. 5); (b) For the 10 MHz to 110 MHz range, an interference-free recording was obtained when the exposure field was reduced to 170 mV/m; and (c) The improved, double-shielded multi-conductor cable produced interference-free recordings at field strength levels of 225 mV/m (fig. 6), and 380 mV/m, respectively, for the frequency ranges in (a) and (b)

Figure 5: "EEG Record" using original single-shielded multi-conductor cable.

Figure 6: "EEG Record" using improved double-shielded multi-conductor cable.

REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHY

Paul S. Ruggera received the BSEE with biomedical option, and the MS in Bioengineering degrees from the University of Wyoming in 1966 and 1968, respectively. Since joining the Bureau of Radiological Health in 1968, he has been

involved in the development and evaluation of near-field rf measurement instrumentation. In the area of EMC, he has published papers discussing: cardiac pacemaker interference associated with various rf and microwave emitters--primarily microwave ovens; E-field strength measurements in the hospital environment; and E- and H-field strength measurements near electrosurgical units, and shortwave and microwave diathermy units.

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